

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-257-IG-20% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	20%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 257
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 10:44:01 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:57:55 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.651	1313157	44.65	114476
2	8.469	148223	5.04	9035
3	12.463	144479	4.91	5655
4	15.045	1335382	45.40	41294

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-251-IG-20% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221014
Vial:	11	Acq. Method Set:	20%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 251
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	19.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 2:14:03 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 3:46:38 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.638	825359	98.36	72215
2	8.446	4285	0.51	372
3	12.388	7994	0.95	330
4	15.086	1504	0.18	72